

Research Article

Farm size and Technical Efficiency of Rice Farmers in Imo State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzed the technical efficiency and the sources of inefficiency in large scale and small scale rice production in Imo State, Nigeria during the 2009 cropping season, using a stochastic frontier production function which incorporates a model for inefficiency effects. A sample of 160 farmers selected using the multi-stage stratified random sampling techniques were used to generate primary data with structured and validated questionnaire through the cost-route approach. Results showed that factors that affected the output of rice farmers were labour, capital, land and planting materials. Low capital base for investment, poor extension contact and poor access to credit were the major factors that influenced farmers' level of technical efficiency. The mean technical efficiency were 0.65 and 0.69 for large and small scale farmers respectively, which implies that the mean technical efficiency index could be increased by 35% and 31% for large scale and small scale farmers respectively through efficient reallocation of the available resources.

Keywords:

Rice farmers, inefficiency factors, stochastic frontier, technical efficiency

INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria, Agriculture is the mainstay of the economy and employs 75% of the work force. Rice forms a significant portion of food consumed in most households in Nigeria. In some countries, the per capita consumption of rice is estimated at more than 100kg / year. Demand for rice production is increasing and greater production is needed to feed more people and reduce the costly imports. Rice is important cereal for human consumption, as it provides 23% of global human per capita energy and 16% of per capita protein (Juliano, 1985). Rice protein contains high lysine and contains amino acid, it is important in making beer, rice-wine, and vinegar. Rice oil extracted from the bran is rich in vitamin E (Ezekiel, et al, 2009).

Unfortunately, the domestic production of rice has not met the demand, leading to food shortage problems. FAO (2003) projected annual growth in rice consumption for Nigeria as 4.5% beyond 2000. In a bid to address the demand/supply gap for rice, the government at various times had come up with policies and programmes such as rice importation to supplement the local production which no doubt continues to drain the country's hard earned foreign exchange earnings. FAO (2008) estimated that Nigerian rice import increases from 2630 tonnes in 1980 to 1876 million tonnes in 2002. The total import also stood at 1.9 million tonnes in 2003 (CBN, 2004).

However, continued fluctuation in rice production in the country is an indication of limited capacity of the Nigeria rice economy to match the domestic demand which can be attributed to the inability of the rice farmers to obtain maximum output from the resources committed to the enterprise (Kolawole, 2010). For instance, an average yield of rice in Nigeria is 1.8 tonnes / hectare compared to 3.0 tonnes / hectare from a country like Cote d'Ivoire and Senegal (WARDA and NISER, 2001). The existing level of production in rice in the country reflects low level of production efficiency of rice farmers in the country as this is a serious problem in achieving food security in the country.

Technical or production efficiency is defined as the ability of making use of implement or mechanical skills to bring about measure of a farm success in producing maximum output for a given set of inputs. It is evident that small scale farmers have consistently remained the major producers of rice in Nigeria, producing over 80 percent of the total rice output (Ohajianya and Onyenweaku, 2002). Yet they are discriminated against in the implementation stage in the scheme of agricultural policies and programmes with the presumption that they are less technically efficient than large scale farmers. But this assumption has not been empirically investigated for rice farmers in Imo state, Nigeria as to warrant the observed disparity in resource inputs allocation and distribution.

Most times, implementation of agricultural policies favours large scale farmers under the presumption that they are more technically efficient than small scale farmers (Dornor, 1972; Khan and

Maki, 1979; Deininger and Binswanger, 1995). Several attempts have been made in Africa to encourage large scale farmers. Examples include, diversion of institutional credit to large farms in Kenya and Malawi (Kydd and Chritiansen, 1982; Lele and Meyers, 1986), subsidization of land settlement irrigation and mechanization costs in Nigeria (Lele and Agarwal, 1989); policy-induced land, labour and output market interventions to favour large European farms over African small holder in Kenya, Zimbabwe and South Africa (Deininger and Binswanger, 1995) or restrictive market differentiation that gave large farms legal rights to grow specific crops for export in Malawi (Christiansen and Kydd, 1987).

Previous studies in Asia have tested for relative efficiency differences by farm size, with conflicting results. Lau and Yotopoulos (1971) and Yotopoulos and Lau (1973) found that small wheat farms in the Indian Punjab were more technically efficient than large farms. In Pakistan, Khan and Maki (1979) found that large farms are more technically efficient than small farms. In Cote d'Ivoire, Adesina and Djato (1996) found no differences in the technical efficiency of small and large farms. Onyenweaku (1997) examined the technical efficiencies of two groups of farms in Kaduna state, Nigeria. The results showed higher level of technical efficiency for large scale farms. The above results on relative technical efficiency suggest the need to avoid generalizations in this regard as what obtains in one country may not follow in another country due to differences in agricultural and institutional settings.

The definition of farm size has been variable in the efficiency literature, as what is considered "large" or "small" is relative depending on the agricultural system settings. In Pakistan agriculture, Khan and Maki (1979) classified large farms as those having 12.5 acres or over 5 hectares. Using Indian data, Yotopoulos and Lau (1973), and Sidhu (1974) classified "large" farms as those with at least 10 acres (i.e. 4 ha). In Nigeria, Olayide et al (1980) described small farms as those farm holdings less than 10 hectares. In a similar study in Cote d'Ivoire, Adesina and Djato (1996) defined large farms as farms of at least 4 hectares. Ohajianya and Onyenweaku (2002), in a similar study, defined large farms as farms of at least 4 hectares. In this study, large scale farmers were defined as farmers that have at least 4 hectares.

This study investigates the technical efficiency and their determinants among rice farmers in Imo state, Nigeria. It is hypothesized that large scale and small scale rice farmers are technically inefficient in rice production.

Theoretical Framework

Previous studies on efficiency of farm can be classified broadly into the following three categories, namely, deterministic parametric estimation, non-parametric mathematical programming and the stochastic parametric estimation (Udo and Akintola, 2001). The use of non-parametric techniques are limited in

efficiency measurements in agriculture despite the fact that non-parametric methodologies can be used in situation where data is more limited and where production technologies are less well understood (Llewelyn and Williams, 1996).

Econometric modeling of stochastic frontier methodology of Aigner, Lovell and Schmidt (1977) associated with the estimation of efficiency has been an important area of research in recent years. Basically, the studies are mostly based on Cobb-Douglas function and transcendental logarithmic (translog) functions that could be specified either as production function or cost function. The first application of stochastic frontier model to farm level agricultural data was by Battese and Corra (1977). But technical efficiency of farms was not directly addressed in the work. Kalirajan (1981) estimated a stochastic frontier Cobb-Douglas production function using cross-sectional data and found the variance of farm effects to be a highly significant component in describing the variability of rice yield. Bagi (1984) used the stochastic frontier Cobb-Douglas production function model to investigate whether there were any significant differences in the mean technical efficiencies of part-time and full-time farmers. Results showed no apparent significance, irrespective of whether the part-time and full-time farmers were engaged in mixed farming or crop cultivation only.

Bagi and Haung (1983) estimated a translogarithmic stochastic frontier production function and found technical efficiencies to vary from 0.35 to 0.92 for mixed farms and 0.52 to 0.91 for crop farms. Kalirajan and Fin (1983) assumed a translogarithmic stochastic frontier production and by maximum likelihood estimation, the parameters were estimated and individual technical efficiencies ranged from 0.38 to 0.91. They went further to regress the predicted technical efficiencies on several farm-level variables and farm-specific characteristics to determine the factors affecting farm level technical efficiencies. In most of the studies, it was found that the Cobb-Douglas stochastic frontier does not provide an adequate representation for describing the data, given specification of a translog model.

The analysis of efficiency is generally associated with the possibility of farms producing a certain optimal level of output from a given bundle of resources at least cost. Farrel (1957) distinguished between three types of efficiency;

(i) Technical Efficiency, which is the physical ratio of product/output to the factor input. The greater the ratio, the greater the magnitude of technical efficiency.

(ii) Allocative or Price Efficiency: A farm is allocatively efficient when production occurs at a point where the marginal value product is equal to the marginal factor cost.

(iii) Economic Efficiency: This is the product of technical and allocative efficiencies. It obtains where both technical and allocative efficiencies have been attained.

The achievement of either technical or allocative efficiency is a necessary but not a sufficient condition to ensuring economic efficiency. He suggested a method of measuring technical efficiency of a farm by estimating the production function of farms which are fully efficient (i.e., a frontier production function). The efficiency however, is bounded between zero and one, where scores of one indicate full efficiency (Tanko, 2009; Ezekiel, et al, 2009; Kolawole, 2009; Udoh and Akintola, 2001; Bagi, 1984; Battese and Coelli, 1995).

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted in Imo state of Nigeria. The state lies within latitudes 50 40' and 70 05' North and longitude 60 35' and 80 30' East (?? Wrong coordinates) (Meteorology Department, Ministry of Lands and Survey, 2004). According to the National Population Commission (NPC, 2006), the population of the state was put at 3.9 million people. The state is divided into three agricultural zones namely; Owerri, Orlu and Okigwe. It is further divided into 27 local Government Areas (LGAs). The state has high agricultural potential with available arable land and soil type that favours the growth of tropical crops such as yam, cassava, maize, rice, cocoyam, plantains, banana and vegetables. Most households keep livestock as part time or full time farmers. The types of livestock kept include sheep, goat, poultry, pigs and rabbit.

A multi-staged sampling technique was employed to select a representative sample. Two LGAs were purposively selected from each of the three agricultural zones due to the more concentration of rice farmers in those LGAs. The sampling frame was the list of registered rice farmers from the selected six LGAs collected from the state office of All Farmers Association of Nigeria (ALFAN) in Owerri. From this sampling frame totaling 203 farmers, stratified into large scale and small scale farmers, a sample size of 160 rice farmers composed of 58 large scale and 102 small scale rice farmers were randomly selected for the study.

Data were collected using structured and validated questionnaire administered on the farm families using the cost-route approach during the 2009 cropping season by trained enumerators under the supervision of the researcher. Data were collected on the socioeconomic characteristics of the farmers, cropping patterns, production activities in terms of inputs, outputs and their prices.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics such as mean, percentages and frequency distribution and the econometric modeling of stochastic production efficiency frontier model independently proposed by Aigner, Lovell and Schmidt (1977) and Meesuen and dan Broek (1977) extended by Jondrow et al (1982) were used in the analysis of data.

The frontier production model begins by considering a stochastic production function with a multiplicative disturbance term of the farm;

$$Y = f(X_i, B)e^E \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

where,
 Y = the quantity of agricultural output
 X_i = vector of input quantities
 B = vector of parameters
 e = error term, and
 E = stochastic disturbance term consisting of two independent elements V and U,
 where,

$$E = U + V \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

The symmetric component V, accounts for random variation in output due to factors outside the farmers control, such as weather and diseases. It is assumed to be independently and identically distributed as N (0, σ²). A one-sided component, V ≤ 0 reflects technical inefficiency relative to the stochastic frontier, and f(X_i, B)e^E. Thus, V=0 for a farm output lying on the frontier and V<0 for one whose output is below the frontier as N (0, σ²) i.e. the distribution of V is half-normal. The frontier of the farm is given by combining (1) and (2) as follows;

$$Y = f(X_i, B)e^{(U+V)} \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Measure of production efficiency for each farm can be calculated as,

$$TE = \exp(-E/u) \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

In the efficiency analysis, the Battese and Coelli (1995) single stage model was applied, whereby V in equation (3) is a non-negative random variable which is the efficiency associated with the technical efficiency factors in production of the sample farmers. It is assumed that the efficiency factors are independently distributed and that V arises by the truncation at zero of the normal distribution, with mean U and variance σ² where V in equation (3) is defined as;

$$V = f(Z_k, \epsilon) \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

where,
 Z_k = vector of farmer-specific factors, and
 ε = vector of parameters

The B and ε coefficients in equation (1) and (5) respectively are unknown parameters to be simultaneously estimated together with the variance parameters which are expressed in the form;

$$r = \epsilon U_2 / (\epsilon U_2, \epsilon V_2) \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

where, r-parameter has a value between zero and one.

Empirical Stochastic Frontier Production Function

The Cobb-Douglas function is specified as;

$$\ln Y_i = b_0 + b_1 \ln X_1 + b_2 \ln X_2 + b_3 \ln X_3 + b_4 \ln X_4 + b_5 \ln X_5 + b_6 \ln X_6 + V_{ij} - U_{ij} \dots\dots(7)$$

where,
 Y_i = the output of rice farmer (kg)
 i = 1 for large scale farmer, 2 for small scale farmer
 X₁ = quantity of planting materials used (kg)
 X₂ = Total quantity of labour used (mandays)
 X₃ = Quantity of fertilizer (kg)
 X₄ = Farm size (ha)
 X₅ = Capital inputs measured in naira and these include depreciation

charges on machinery, equipment, interest charges on borrowed capital, tractor hiring and irrigation charges.

X_6 = Expenditure on agrochemicals (₦)

V_{ij} =Random error term independently and identically distributed, have a normal distribution with mean zero and variance, σ^2 intended to capture events beyond the control of the farmers.

U_{ij} = a non-negative random technical efficiency effects associated with the technical efficiency of farmers involved. It is assumed to arise from a normal distribution with mean U_{ij} and variance σ^2 which is truncated at zero.

B_0 = intercept term

b_1 - b_6 = parameters estimated by the maximum likelihood method using the computer program, LIMDEP, (Battese and Coelli, 1992).

Sources of Inefficiency

the function of socioeconomic factors (Yao and Liu, 1998) as given in equation (8).

It is assumed that the technical inefficiency measure by the mode of truncated normal distribution (i.e., U_{ij}) is

$$U_{ij}=a_0 + a_1Z_1 + a_2Z_2 + a_3Z_3 + a_4Z_4 + a_5Z_5 + a_6Z_6 + a_7Z_7 + a_8Z_8 \dots(8)$$

where,

U_{ij} =Technical inefficiency of i th farmer and j th observation on the farmer

Z_1 =capital invested in rice production (₦)

Z_2 = extension contact (No. of visits)

Z_3 = access to credit (dummy variable, 1 for access, zero for no access to credit)

Z_4 = farming experience (years)

Z_5 = Household size (No. of persons)

Z_6 = level of education (No. years spent in school)

Z_7 = membership of cooperative (dummy variable, 1 for membership, Zero for-membership)

Z_8 = Age of the farmer (years)

a_0 = constant term

a_1 - a_8 = parameters that were estimated by the maximum likelihood, using computer program, (Battese and Coeli, 1992).

The variables included in this model as the determinants of technical efficiency were indicated by possible effects of farmer's personal characteristics and farming conditions on technical efficiency.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socioeconomic Characteristics of Rice Farmers

Table 1 shows that 89.7% of the large scale farmers and 71.6% of the small scale farmers were males while only 10.3% of the large scale and 28.4% of the small scale farmers were females. The larger proportion of respondents was male, indicating that rice production was dominated by males in the study area. Majority (74.1%) of large scale and (77.5%) of small scale rice farmers fell in the age bracket of 41-51 years, which could be classified as the active and productive age. Also 55.2% of large scale and 50% of

small scale farmers had household sizes of 9-12 persons, which implies that most of the labour force would be supplied by the household members.

Educationally, 56.9% of the large scale and 57.9% of the small scale farmers spent 7-12 years in formal education, which implies that the rate of adoption of innovation is expected to be high in the study area. Also, 48.3% of the large scale and 46.1% of the small scale farmers have been in rice production for 11-15 years, which implies that many of the farmers have acquired enough experience in rice production to enable them earn higher profit and allocate resources more efficiently in rice production.

On extension contact, 60.3% of the large scale and 48% of the small scale farmers had 1-2 visits per annum, which implies that extension visits to the rice farmers were poor in the study area. It was found that 96.5% of the large scale and 95.1% of the small scale farmers were married, which indicates how responsible the farmers were to their various households.

Table 1. Socio-Economic Characteristics of rice farmers

Socioeconomic characteristics		Large scale (n=58)		Small scale (n=102)	
		Frequency	percentage	Frequency	percentage
Sex	Male	52	89.7	73	71.6
	Female	6	10.3	29	28.4
Age	30-40	8	13.8	10	9.8
	41-51	43	74.1	79	77.5
	52-62	5	8.6	5	4.9
	63 and above	2	3.5	8	7.8
Household	1-4	7	12.1	16	15.7
	5-8	9	15.5	21	28.6
	9-12	32	55.2	51	50.0
	13 and above	10	17.2	14	13.7
Level of education	0 (No formal education)	3	5.2	1	0.9
	1-6	14	24.1	23	22.6
	7-12	33	56.9	59	57.9
	13-18	8	13.8	19	18.6
Farming experience	6-10	5	8.6	8	7.8
	11-15	28	48.3	47	46.1
	16-20	8	13.8	22	21.6
	21-25	9	15.5	20	19.6
	26-30	8	13.8	5	4.9

Table 1 Continues

Extension contact	0 (no visits)	19	32.8	21	20.6
	1-2	35	60.3	49	48.0
	3-4	3	5.2	23	22.6
	5-6	1	1.7	9	8.8
Marital status	Single	2	3.5	5	4.9
	Married	56	96.5	97	95.1
Sources of credit	Friends/relatives	6	10.3	9	8.8
	Cooperative	7	12.1	15	14.7
	Thrift society	11	18.9	20	19.6
	Personal savings	23	39.7	29	28.5
	Banks	9	15.5	24	23.5
	Money lenders	2	3.5	5	4.9

Source: field data, 2009

The study formed that 39.7% of the large scale and 28.5% of the small scale farmers obtained the funds for their production activities through their personal savings, which implies that the formal credit institutions were not being utilized possibly due to their stringent loan conditions.

Maximum Likelihood Estimates of Factors Affecting Output of Rice Farmers

Table 2 presents the Maximum Likelihood Estimates (MLE) of the stochastic production frontier. The parameter estimates of the MLE related to quantity of planting materials (X_1), total quantity of labour used (X_2) and land or farm size (X_4) were statistically significant at 1% level of probability for the two farm types, while capital inputs (X_5) was significant at 5% level of probability for both large scale and small scale rice farmers, implying that these variables are the factors affecting output of rice farmers in Imo State.

The coefficients for quantity of fertilizer (X_3), and expenditure on agro-chemicals (X_6) were not

statistically significant at 5% level of probability, implying that these variables are not important factors affecting output of rice farmers in Imo State.

The values of returns to scale were 2.255 and 2.011 for the large scale and small scale rice farmers respectively, which implies increasing returns to scale, indicating that an increase in the use of the selected variables would result in more than proportionate increase in the production of rice.

The value of sigma squared were 0.651 and 0.593 for large scale and small scale farmers which are equally statistically significant at 5% level of probability indicating a good fit and correctness of the distribution assumption specified. The variance of the ratio (Gamma) which measures the effects of technical efficiency in the variation of observed output has values of 0.324 and 0.353 for large scale and small scale farmers respectively, which means that 32% and 35% of the total variation in the output of rice farmers is due to technical inefficiency.

Table 2. Maximum Likelihood Estimates of Factors Affecting Output of Rice Farmers.

Variables	Large scale	Small scale
Constant	29.016	25.349
Quantity of planting Materials used (X_1)	0.279 (3.187)**	0.263 (2.964)**
Total quantity of labour used (X_2)	0.658 (2.873)**	0.571 (3.006)**
Quantity of fertilizer (X_5)	0.173 (1.557)	0.184 (1.693)
Farm size (X_4)	0.866 (2.879)**	0.692 (3.116)**
Capital inputs (X_5)	0.238 (2.473)*	0.249 (2.512)*
Expenditure on agro-chemicals (X_6)	0.041 (1.837)	0.052 (1.914)
Returns to scale	2.255	2.011
Diagnostic statistics		
Sigma square	0.651	0.593

Table 2 Continues

	(2.544)*	(2.394)*
Gamma	0.324	0.353
	(2.523)*	(2.489)*
Log-likelihood function	-61.039	-54.013

Figures in parentheses are t-ratios

*Significant at 5%

**Significant at 1%

Source: field data, 2009

Technical Efficiency

The levels of technical efficiency in rice production in Imo State are summarized in table 3. The table shows that 34.5% of the large scale and 36.4% of the small scale farmers had technical efficiency levels of 0.51-0.60, while only 5.2% of the large scale and 9.8% of the small scale farmers had technical efficiency levels

of 0.91-1.00. Also, 17.2% of the large scale and 4.9% of the small scale farmers operated at a technical efficiency level of not more than 0.50. The mean levels of technical efficiency for the large scale and small scale rice farmers are less than 1.00, indicating that all the farmers are producing below the maximum technical efficiency frontier.

Table 3. Distribution of Rice Farmers According to Level of Technical Efficiency

Efficiency class	Large scale		Small scale	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
≤0.50	10	17.2	5	4.9
0.51-0.60	20	34.5	37	36.4
0.61-0.70	4	6.9	20	19.6
0.71-0.80	18	31.0	18	17.4
0.81-0.90	3	5.2	12	11.9
0.91-1.00	3	5.2	10	9.8
Total	58	100	102	100
Mean	0.654		0.686	

Source: field data, 2009

Therefore the hypothesis which states that large scale and small scale rice farms are technically inefficient is hereby accepted. The results of mean technical efficiency imply that the large scale and small scale farmers are able to get a little over 65% and 69% respectively of potential output from a given mix of

production inputs, suggesting a scope for improvement by reallocating existing resources more optimally.

Results further show that it will take an average large scale rice farmer in the survey area $(1 - 0.65/58) \times 100$ (112%), and average small scale rice farmer in the survey area $(1 - 0.69/102) \times 100$ (68%)

cost saving to become the most technically efficient farmer.

Estimates of Parameters of Efficiency Factors

The results of analysis on sources of inefficiency in rice production are presented in table 4. The results indicate that capital invested (Z_1), extension contact (Z_2) and access to credit (Z_3) are the only significant determinants of the level of technical efficiency in rice production in the study area. The coefficient of capital invested was negative and significant at 1% level, which implies that if the capital base is low it leads to increase in level of inefficiency of rice farmers.

The coefficient of extension contact was negative and significant at 1% level. This negative sign does not conform to prior expectation, because previous findings have indicated that extension contact have a positive contribution in influencing the behavioural orientation of the farmer to improved farm

practices which in turn leads to increase in efficiency of production. Extension contact with farmers enhance acquisition of new knowledge, skill and practices on improved technology by the farmers as well as their innovativeness (Dey, 2001; Tanko and Olowogbaji 2009) which is expected to translate into increased outputs. Contacts with extension agents afford the farmers the opportunity of sharing ideas and information on modern rice production practices by interacting with other farmers. This finding is not consistent with earlier results by Ajibefun and Daramola (2003) who found out that the coefficient with respect to extension contact is positive. This suggests that the extension services are not adequate in the survey area given the recommended extension agent to farmer ratio.

The estimated coefficient of access to credit was negative and significant at 5%, which implies that poor access to credit leads to increase in level of technical inefficiency of rice farmers in the study area.

Table 4. Maximum Likelihood Estimates Of the Parameters Of the Inefficiency Factors in Rice Production.

Variable	Parameter	Coefficient	
		Large scale	Small scale
Constant	a_0	-3.094 (-4.117)**	-2.809 (-3.861)**
Capital invested (Z_1)	a_1	-0.166 (-3.103)**	-0.103 (-2.816)**
Extension contact (Z_2)	a_2	-0.039 (-2.718)**	-0.047 (-2.803)**
Access to credit (Z_3)	a_3	-0.081 (-2.522)*	-0.073 (-2.416)*
Farming experience (Z_4)	a_4	0.108 (1.609)	0.105 (1.712)
Household size (Z_5)	a_5	-0.097 (-1.826)	-0.076 (-1.902)
Level of education (Z_6)	a_6	0.138 (1.556)	0.115 (1.667)
Membership of cooperative (Z_7)	a_7	0.052 (1.743)	0.034 (1.811)
Age of the farmer (Z_8)	a_8	-0.131 (-1.903)	-0.102 (-1.816)

Figures in parentheses are t-ratios

*Significant at 5%, **Significant at 1%, Source: field data, 2009

CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

This study analyzed the technical efficiency and the sources of inefficiency in large scale and small scale rice production in Imo State. The maximum likelihood estimation results showed that labour, capital, land and planting material are the major factors significantly explaining changes in the output of rice farmers. The mean levels of technical efficiency for large scale and small scale farmers were 0.65 and 0.69 respectively. The low capital base for investment, poor extension contact and poor access to credit are the major factors that influenced the levels of their technical efficiency. The distribution of the technical efficiency indices suggest that the current state of technology used by the farmers is inferior and grossly inadequate to bring about significant increases in rice production in Imo

State. Therefore, there is need for the adoption of a more superior rice production technology.

The implication of the study is that the mean technical efficiency index could be increased by 35% and 31% for large scale and small scale farmers respectively through efficient reallocation of the available resources.

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